

Contemporary Islamic Educational Thought; Aligning Traditions with Global Changes

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ABSTRACT: Contemporary Islamic education plays a crucial role in navigating the challenges and changes Muslims face in this era of globalization. This article aims to illustrate how modern Islamic educational thought strives to align traditional values with the dynamics of global changes. The analysis is conducted using the library research method. This study employs content analysis methods to investigate various thoughts and views that emerge from contemporary Islamic education thinkers. The analysis results show that despite the complex challenges faced, contemporary Islamic education thought offers valuable insights into how Islamic education can remain relevant and meaningful in facing global realities. By aligning tradition with global changes, Islamic education can be more effective in shaping critical thinkers as ethical and competitive individuals in the modern world. This article highlights several strategies proposed by Islamic education thinkers to facilitate the alignment between tradition and global changes. These strategies include (1) Developing a relevant curriculum, (2) Utilizing technology in learning, and (3) Adopting a contextual learning approach. It involves integrating foundational Islamic values with contemporary contexts and demands, using information and communication technology to enhance the accessibility and quality of education, and emphasizing inclusive and progressive educational approaches.

KEYWORDS: Contemporary Islamic education, Tradition, Global Changes

A. INTRODUCTION

Islamic education has been an integral part of the intellectual heritage of Muslims for centuries. However, in this turbulent era of globalization, new challenges have emerged that test the relevance and effectiveness of Islamic education in addressing the rapid dynamics of change. Globalization brings information, values, and technologies that shape the global educational landscape. At the same time, maintaining the authenticity and uniqueness of Islamic teachings remains a priority for many Muslim communities.

Globalization is part of the development of information technology that structurally changes human life patterns, ranging from economic, social, and cultural to political aspects. In the financial field, it has implemented international trade, foreign investors, and global markets that connect various countries from different continents. Information technology, advancing daily and becoming more sophisticated, always presents multiple features that facilitate human life in meeting daily needs. Of course, it changes how humans will work, learn, and interact socially in the future.. (Abdullah, 2018)

The influence of globalization is also felt in the field of education. Students now have the opportunity to study at international educational institutions, access global educational resources, and take courses online. This facilitates a broader exchange of knowledge and increases the availability of education. (Bank, 2021) Islamic education faces various changes that demand adaptation and enhancement to keep up with these dynamics. Advances in science and technology are one of the challenges for Islamic education, especially in the era of globalization, which narrows the distance and time in the exchange of information and knowledge between countries, particularly in the context of Islamic education. The development of science and technology has created various media that can be utilized to improve Islamic education. Previously, Islamic education was limited to local communities and had limited quality. However, with the advent of multimedia, especially the internet, Islamic education has become more widely accessible, in a shorter time, and with better quality. (Sulaeman, 2015)

In this context, contemporary Islamic educational thought becomes increasingly important as an effort to align traditional values with the demands of global changes. Through this research, we aim to explore various thoughts, strategies, and views that emerge from contemporary Islamic education thinkers and to analyze how these concepts can be practically implemented in the current educational context.

By examining changes in the global education paradigm, including the role of technology, shifting job market demands, and complex social and political dynamics, we can understand the urgency of adaptation in Islamic educational thought. Through an

Contemporary Islamic Educational Thought; Aligning Traditions with Global Changes

open and innovative approach, Islamic education can survive and thrive as a force driving positive change in Muslim communities and the world at large.

B. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The method used in this research is library research, a series of activities conducted to collect sources used in the study through libraries. (Mahmud, 2011) Library research is a technique used to collect data by analyzing various journals, notes, books, and research related to the issues discussed. (Nazir, 2003) Several procedures are used to gather the necessary information, including reading multiple sources, making notes, and processing the data obtained so that the data is first processed and analyzed before concluding. (Zed, Mestika, 2008) In collecting data from a study, several sources are used, including magazines, journals, books, and necessary information, as well as documentation during the observation and data collection stages in the field, such as photos, notes, and images.

C. DISCUSSION AND RESEARCH FINDING

1. Contemporary Islamic Thought

Contemporary Islamic thought in Indonesia encompasses diverse perspectives and views that have evolved within Indonesian Muslim society and academia today. Over the past few decades, Islamic thought in Indonesia has undergone significant development in response to social, political, and economic changes at the national and global levels.

One of the main characteristics of contemporary Islamic thought in Indonesia is the ideological and methodological diversity reflected in the broad spectrum of Islamic traditions, ranging from traditional pesantren traditions to modernist, reformist, and progressive perspectives. Some prominent figures in contemporary Islamic thought in Indonesia include Nurcholish Madjid, Abdurrahman Wahid (Gus Dur), Azyumardi Azra, Ulil Abshar Abdalla, Komaruddin Hidayat, and many others.

Contemporary Islamic thought in Indonesia often focuses on critical issues such as democracy, human rights, pluralism, interfaith relations, Islamic feminism, ecology, and other global challenges. Some contemporary Islamic thinkers strive to align Islamic values with the principles of democracy and modernity, while others emphasize the importance of contextual and dynamic interpretations of Islamic texts.

The main challenges faced by contemporary Islamic thought in Indonesia include finding a balance between adherence to Islamic values and the demands of rapid social progress and change and responding to the challenges of extremism and intolerance that sometimes emerge in society. Thus, contemporary Islamic thought in Indonesia reflects the complexity of Indonesia's culture and history and is an essential contribution to the global dialogue about Islam in a continuously changing world.

The emergence of various Islamic phenomena shows the variations in understanding, background, boundaries, and characteristics of each Islamic thought movement in Indonesia. Each movement has its unique characteristics and identity. Below are some variations in contemporary Islamic thought movements described. (Malli, n/d)

a) Fundamentalist Islam

Fundamentalist Islam is a flow or approach in Islam that emphasizes literal or literal interpretation of Islamic holy texts, such as the Koran and Hadith, as well as reaffirmation of the principles and values considered fundamental in the Islamic religion. The main characteristics of fundamentalist Islam include the rejection of modernization and secularization, as well as the desire to return to a model of life that was considered an ideal example in the early days of Islam, such as the model of life during the time of the Prophet Muhammad and his companions.

Fundamentalist Islam often views that a correct understanding of Islam can only be obtained through emphasizing rigid and uncompromising teachings, as well as rejecting cultural influences or values that are considered contrary to Islamic teachings. However, it is essential to note that the term fundamentalist is often considered to have negative connotations, mainly when used to describe extreme or intolerant religious sects or understandings. Many scholars believe that not all sects that emphasize fundamental aspects of their religion can be called fundamentalist in the pejorative sense.

b) Neo-traditionalist Islam

Neo-traditionalist Islam is an approach or school of Islamic thought that tries to synthesize Islamic traditions with the modern or contemporary context. The term "neo-traditionalist" indicates an attempt to restore the authenticity and truth of traditional Islamic values while simultaneously recognizing the reality of changing times and adopting a more contextual approach. The main characteristic of neo-traditionalist Islam is the emphasis on the importance of understanding and practicing the teachings of Islam in the current context without ignoring the roots and traditional values of Islam. They often advocate a balanced approach between Islam's rich heritage and the need to adapt to modern society's social, economic, and political changes.

Neo-traditionalist Islam also often emphasizes the importance of tolerance, interreligious dialogue, and social welfare within the framework of a contextual and inclusive understanding of Islam. They seek to bridge the gap between tradition and modernity by creating space for a more flexible interpretation of Islam's sacred texts. Although there are variations in thought and approach within it, neo-traditionalist Islam generally tries to answer contemporary challenges by referring to values and principles originating from Islamic traditions while considering today's context and realities.

Contemporary Islamic Educational Thought; Aligning Traditions with Global Changes

c) Neo-modernist Islam

Neo-modernist Islam is a flow or approach to Islamic thought that tries to adapt Islamic teachings to the principles of modernity, including democracy, human rights, pluralism, and science. The term "neo-modernist" denotes an attempt to bring Islam into the mainstream of modern thought. The main characteristic of neo-modernist Islam is its emphasis on contextual and dynamic interpretation of Islamic sacred texts, such as the Koran and Hadith, considering the current context and the social, economic, and political changes occurring. They interpret Islamic teachings in the context of contemporary reality and attempt to answer today's challenges using the principles of modernity.

Neo-modernist Islam often rejects literal or literal interpretations of sacred texts, and they tend to view that Islam can synergize with the universal values that modern society strives for. They also often fight for reform in various fields, such as education, law, economics, and social affairs, to improve social conditions and advance society. However, neo-modernist approaches have not always been universally accepted within the Islamic world and have often been controversial and debated. Some groups or sects within Islam still maintain traditional views and reject efforts to modernize their religious teachings.

d) Liberal Islam

Liberal Islam is a school or approach in Islamic thought that emphasizes an open and flexible interpretation of Islamic sacred texts and places universal values such as individual freedom, gender equality, pluralism, and democracy as the primary foundation in understanding religion. The main characteristic of liberal Islam is its emphasis on a contextual and progressive interpretation of Islamic teachings, considering modern values and the social, economic, and political developments that occur. Liberal Muslims tend to reject literal or literal interpretations of sacred texts, and they argue that Islam must be able to adapt to the universal values held by modern society.

Liberal Islam also often fights for individual rights, including the rights of women and minorities, and calls for reform in various aspects of social, economic, and political life. They strive to make Islam a source of inspiration for social and humanitarian progress, emphasizing values such as justice, peace, and tolerance. Although liberal Islam offers an innovative and inclusive interpretation of Islam, this approach is often the subject of controversy among Muslims, especially in countries where conservative Islamic traditions are still dominant. Several groups or sects within Islam reject the liberal approach and view it as a form of deviation from religious teachings.

2. Global Changes in Islamic Education

Globalization is not only limited to economic aspects but also has significant consequences in the social, cultural, and educational domains, including Islamic education, which spreads worldwide. To get a better understanding, let's examine some of the impacts of globalization listed below: (Alamsyah, 2023)

- a) The impact of globalization on Islamic education is also significant. Along with increasing access to global information, Islamic education is now expanded beyond the local scope. It raises questions about how to combine local values with global values in the Islamic learning process and how to maintain the relevance of Islamic education in an increasingly connected and diverse world. (Appadurai, 1996)
- b) Globalization has had an impact on learning methods in Islamic education. Today, teachers and students have broader access to international educational resources, enabling more interactive and technology-based learning methods. However, this also requires in-depth consideration of how religious values can be integrated into an increasingly global curriculum. (Castells, 1996)
- c) One of the challenges that is a necessity is the integration of local traditional values against global change by maintaining Islamic insight along with developments in the world of science that has developed in the era of globalization. It is an important thing to pay attention to because it will have an impact on the lives of people who live in global change but do not deny their local traditions (Held, David, et al., 1999)

Global influence in Islamic education can be manifested in several significant aspects. Globalization has opened more comprehensive access to information and knowledge about Islam. Through the internet and social media, pupils and students can easily access sources of Islamic knowledge from various parts of the world. It allows for a faster and broader exchange of ideas and thoughts.

Globalization brings cultural influences from various countries and cultures into Islamic education. Values, practices, and popular culture outside the Islamic tradition may influence Islamic educational institutions. It can affect the way Islam is taught and understood. Information and communication technology development has changed how Islamic education is delivered and studied. The use of technology in teaching, such as e-learning, webinars, and Islamic education applications, has increased the efficiency and accessibility of Islamic education worldwide.

Globalization has also increased openness and pluralism in Islamic education. Islamic educational institutions may have to accommodate students from various cultural, ethnic, and religious backgrounds. This encourages adopting an inclusive and respectful approach to diversity in Islamic education. Globalization also brings challenges and opportunities for Islamic education. On the one hand, Islamic education faces the challenge of maintaining the authenticity of religious teachings in the face of global cultural influences that may conflict with Islamic values. However, globalization also opens up opportunities for collaboration

Contemporary Islamic Educational Thought; Aligning Traditions with Global Changes

between Islamic educational institutions worldwide and a more comprehensive exchange of knowledge and experience. Global Changes in Islamic Education.

3. Local Values in Islamic Education

The importance of local traditional values in Islamic education towards global changes should not be ignored. Local traditional values play an essential role in shaping the identity and sustainability of Islamic education amidst the continuous flow of global change. Although the importance of local conventional values is acknowledged, it is also important to note that Islamic education must be able to integrate local values with relevant global values. It allows Islamic education to remain relevant and sustainable in facing the challenges of complex global change. As for understanding local values in Islamic education, you can pay attention to the following things:

a) Local and cultural values in Islamic society

Local and cultural values in Islamic society are a valuable inheritance passed down from generation to generation. Understanding and maintaining these values in Islamic education significantly shapes students' overall character. Social solidarity is a central value in Islamic society, reflecting the principle of brotherhood emphasized in Islamic teachings. (Muhammad, 2018)

As explained above, in this case, it can reflect a caring and responsible attitude in the community so that students can master various sciences with the religious culture around them. Ethics plays a crucial role in Islamic culture because it contains the values of honesty, courtesy, and tolerance. Implementing these ethical values can positively impact students' daily lives in society. (Ali, 2019)

b) The influence of local values on Islamic education and character formation

Globalization has significantly impacted Islamic education; it is related to easy access to information from various media platforms and even culture from various other parts of the world, thus challenging local traditional values. (Amen, 2021)

Local wisdom values can be understood in terms of a culture that has a unique history. Still, globalization brings peace, justice, and human values, so in this case, there is a need for an approach based on multiculturalism to integrate these values when learning takes place. (Hasan, 2020)

The influence of local values on Islamic education and character formation is very significant in developing individuals with noble character. It reflects the cultural roots and values inherent in the society where Islamic education is implemented. The influence of local values on Islamic education and character formation illustrates the importance of strengthening cultural roots in the development of individuals who have good morals and contribute positively to society.

c) Globalization and value harmonization approach

Understanding how Islamic education can adopt an approach that harmoniously aligns with local and global values is essential. It includes efforts to combine unique Islamic values with universal values such as peace, justice, and humanity that are recognized globally. The significance of this harmonization lies in its ability to overcome the division between local and global values.

This approach can be implemented through changes to the Islamic education curriculum, which emphasizes the harmonization of values and teacher training to deliver education that combines local and global values in a balanced manner. This way, Islamic education links local communities and an increasingly interconnected global world. (Hassan, 2019)

d) Multicultural learning in Islamic education

Islamic education can incorporate multicultural elements to facilitate students' exploration of cultural and religious diversity while maintaining an understanding of distinctive Islamic values. Through case studies on implementing multicultural education in Islamic learning, we can better understand effective practices in creating an inclusive and diverse educational environment. (Rahman, 2021)

This approach also involves developing a curriculum that includes learning about other cultures and religions and training teachers in applying multicultural approaches to teaching. These steps help students to gain an understanding and appreciation of diversity, as well as promote human solidarity and peace in an increasingly heterogeneous society. (Abdullah, 2018)

e) Preparing critical and ethical individuals

Critical thinking ability is the skill to evaluate, analyze, and formulate arguments logically and rationally. This skill is very relevant in the global era, where a lot of information is available, and the ability to sort accurate information from inaccurate information becomes very important. Research shows that Islamic education can significantly impact students' critical thinking skills development. (Faisal, 2021)

Ethics has a fundamental role in shaping individual behavior and actions. Islamic education can facilitate the development of students' understanding of ethics related to religious teachings, morality, and social values. It is essential to form individuals who act ethically in various global contexts. Islamic education can be the foundation for profoundly understanding values, ethics, and morality..

4. Strategies for Aligning Tradition with Global Change

The approach in educational strategy to align tradition with global change includes several things, namely:

a. Appropriate (Relevant) Curriculum Development

Contemporary Islamic Educational Thought; Aligning Traditions with Global Changes

The era of globalization is a process of change between countries, between nations, and between cultures without knowing borders. The influence of this era of globalization is increasingly felt, especially with the increasing number of information channels available, both print and electronic, as well as rapid developments in the fields of technology, communication, and transportation. (Ervina., 2020)

The importance of curriculum development requires a planned strategy to ensure good quality. The initial stage is to process the adoption of curriculum materials from various sources, both informally for personal use and formally for the use of others, with a documented and accountable process.

Steps in developing a curriculum that is appropriate or relevant in the current era of globalization include Needs analysis, which means identifying student needs to determine the curriculum's objectives and content to suit today's times. Research and Consultation: this is done to discover global trends, technology, and needs in the field. Curriculum development includes designing a curriculum with 21st-century skills such as problem-solving, creativity, and cross-cultural cooperation. Technology integration, with the use of technology, increases access to learning effectiveness and teaches digital skills. Flexibility and Adaptation: this includes a curriculum design that can adapt to rapid changes in the global environment, including culture. The last one is evaluation and renewal, which helps ensure the curriculum remains relevant, practical, and ready to be adapted to suit the desired needs.

A holistic approach is needed to maintain the relevance of education amidst the dynamics of global change. First, the curriculum must be adapted to international demands, covering aspects such as technology, multiculturalism, and sustainability. However, the essence of traditional values, such as ethics, morality, and local wisdom, must be integrated in a contemporary way. Collaboration between government, academia, industry, and local communities is critical to ensuring curricula reflect global needs while respecting local values. It is also essential for educators to receive adequate training to be able to implement these two aspects effectively in the daily learning process.

b. Use of Technology in Learning

Technological developments have contributed to changing learning styles, especially using learning media. (Budiyono, n/d) According to KBBI, educational technology is a systematic method for planning, using, and assessing all teaching and learning activities by paying attention to technical and human resources and the interaction between the two to obtain a more effective form of education. The main goal of educational technology as learning is to solve all learning problems by facilitating learning to improve the quality of education itself. It will also meet the learning needs of society by creating a learning system and pattern that will directly impact economic, social, and scientific development activities. (Fitri, 2022)

Technology use is no longer strange in the era of globalization. In the world of education, as the birthplace of technology, it is only natural that education also utilizes technology to facilitate the implementation of learning. From here, the term educational technology emerged. Educational technology is a systematic planning method that assesses all teaching and learning activities by paying attention to technical and human resources and the interaction between the two to obtain a more effective form of education (Big Dictionary Indonesian). (S, 2018)

One solution or approach to harmonize education by utilizing technology in learning while still maintaining tradition is to create learning content that combines modern technology with local values, such as folklore or traditional ceremonies. Training teachers to properly use technology is also essential to ensure good integration without sacrificing traditional values. Collaboration with local communities is also needed to ensure harmonization between the use of technology and cultural values. c. Contextual Learning Approach

Contextual learning can improve student learning outcomes. Learning that actively involves students will help and make it easier for students to understand and remember what they are and have learned in class. They can also be used as a guide or basis for their daily lives in society related to their local culture. However, conventional learning carried out by teachers still uses the old paradigm, namely teacher-centered; teachers still dominate learning activities and do not fully involve students. (Wahyuni, et al, 2013)

This contextual learning model guides students to find the meaning of the material studied as an experience to build existing knowledge. In this context, students need to understand what learning means, its benefits, their status, and how to achieve it. Implementing contextual learning makes students aware that what is learned in the classroom will be helpful for their later lives because this model is more likely to provide accurate and meaningful experiences for students. Implementing this contextual learning model aims to provide knowledge and expertise close to students' daily lives. Learning involves not transferring knowledge from teachers to students but rather work and experience. This process will take place more naturally in the form of student activities. (Romli, n/d)

To align education with a contextual learning approach in local and global traditions is to design a curriculum that includes local and universal values, develop diverse learning materials, utilize technology and digital resources, involve local communities in the learning process, use a project-based learning approach, as well as encouraging intercultural collaboration in the classroom. In this way, students can experience learning that is relevant to their reality and broaden their horizons about the world globally..

D. DISCUSSION

We are integrating underlying Islamic values with context. 25 era, information and communication technology use and an inclusive and progressive educational approach are critical aspects of this effort. The importance of adaptation and innovation in Islamic educational thinking cannot be ignored. By continuing to respond to the dynamics of global change, Islamic education can remain relevant and meaningful in forming individuals who think critically and ethically and are competitive in the modern world.

However, the challenges faced are not easy, and a strong commitment is needed from all relevant parties to continue to develop contemporary Islamic educational thinking. This conclusion underscores the importance of collaboration between academics, educational practitioners, and other stakeholders to design effective strategies and policies for changing global realities..

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